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Prof. Dr. Azilah Bt Kasim

Co-Guest Editors

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Rozila Ahmad

Dr. Eshaby binti Mustafa

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FOREWORD

The issue of sustainability has never been more relevant than today as many negative environmental impacts such as pollution of natural resources and large carbon footprints are becoming more pronounced. This is attributed to the activities and greed of humans who do not appreciate the natural environment. It is therefore critical for aspects that are directly or indirectly related to United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to be discussed by academics as well as the industry. Held virtually on 27-28 September 2020, Langkawi Tourism and Hospitality International Conference (LTHIC 2020) was organised by Universiti Utara Malaysia's School of Education's (SOE) Langkawi International Tourism and Hospitality (LITH) Research Centre dan School of Tourism, Hospitality and Event Management's (STHEM) Event Management Research Unit (EMRU), with the collaboration of Sekolah Tinggi Pariwisata Mataram, Lombok, Indonesia.

The conference has several goals, namely as a platform for the development of new ideas as well as knowledge sharing on sustainable development from local and foreign experts in related fields. The conference also provided an opportunity for academics, industry activists, postgraduate students, and stakeholders to exchange views and discuss the salient and insightful points raised on the sustainability of the tourism and hospitality industry. Originally planned to be held in Langkawi, Kedah, the conference was finally held virtually due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This conference was participated by academics from various local and overseas institutions including Sekolah Tinggi Pariwisata Mataram, University of Baltistan, Skardu, University of Santo Tomas, Universitas Negeri Padang, Politeknik Pariwisata Palembang, Nakhon Si Thammarat Rajabhat University, Politeknik Tuanku Syed Sirajuddin as well as staff and students of Universiti Utara Malaysia. The conference produced 30 full papers that have been published in this journal.

Professor Dr. Azilah Kasim, CHT, C.NLP

*Chairperson, Langkawi Tourism and Hospitality International Conference 2020
(LTHIC 2020)*

*Director of Langkawi International Tourism and Hospitality (LITH) Research Center
Universiti Utara Malaysia, Malaysia*

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Community Involvement and Participation for Sustainable Tourism: A Case Study in Gili Trawangan Post-earthquake

I Made Murdana, Syamsul Alam Paturusi, Anak Agung Putra Suryawan Wiranata, Halus Mandala and Gusti Ayu Oka Suryawardani
Sekolah Tinggi Pariwisata Mataram, Indonesia

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Abstract: The locus of study is the Gili Trawangan Nature Reserve (Gili Tramen National Natural Park) which is located in the North Lombok municipality under the West Nusa Tenggara (*Nusa Tenggara Barat/NTB*) province of Indonesia. Sustainable tourism has long been viewed as beneficial to the environment, community, and economy. Further studies confirmed that community participation has a role and is an important tenet of tourism planning. While community empowerment and social capital have always been hot research areas in tourism development, only a few studies have explored the implementation of community involvement and participation, especially after the 2018 earthquake. The aim of this study was to determine the forms of involvement and participation of local communities in the recovery and sustainability of Gili Trawangan tourist destinations under the Tosun theory approach. This study used a qualitative approach. In-depth interviews were the method used to gather data through key respondents (purposive sampling). The study asserted that the community involvement and participation approach was a strategy to encourage recovery and to sustain the nature park of Gili Tramen. The study found that community involvement and participation formed significantly after the earthquake. The type of community participation was dominated by spontaneous participation, and this study showed that the recovery of Gili Trawangan was a great success. The findings of this research served as a recommendation to the government, investors, and stakeholders on the approach strategy in Gili Trawangan's development.

Keywords: Community participation, community involvement, community-based tourism (CBT), sustainable tourism, resilience, responsible tourism

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Correspondence: I Made Murdana, Sekolah Tinggi Pariwisata Mataram, Indonesia.
Email: mmurdana@gmail.com

Introduction

In the last two decades, the issue of sustainability has been a topic of discussion and debate among researchers in relation to development, particularly in the tourism sector (Byrd, 2007; Vles, 2009). The principles of sustainability are pivotal in the implementation of future development, especially in local communities. Sustainability is a solution offered by many researchers because it has long been considered beneficial for the environment, community, and economy (Gibson, Kaplanidou, & Kang, 2012; Swarbrooke, 1999). The three benefits of sustainability are popularly known as the dimensions of sustainability. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development has a global commitment towards successfully achieving sustainable development in the three domains of economic, social, and environment, in a balanced and integrated manner (United Nations, 2015).

There are many obstacles in the implementation of sustainability in the field of tourism, especially with respect to the community (Aref & Redzuan, 2008; Dogra & Gupta, 2012). The community is the part which is often marginalised. However, various gaps become apparent with community involvement. For instance, local communities tend not to be directly involved in tourism development, be it in the planning or decision-making process. The community also considers the enjoyment of benefits brought about by tourism to be limited to business people and government officials rather than being used for the benefit of the entire community. Nevertheless, scholars have paid much attention to the rationality of local community involvement and participation. This includes the need for the community to be active in the growth of tourism during the planning and decision-making process, for example (Gumede & Nzama, 2019; Moyo & Tichaawa, 2017; Muganda, Sirima, & Ezra, 2013; Sebele, 2010; Tosun, 1999, 2006; Yu, Chancellor, & Cole, 2011). Research has presented questions about the unsustainable and ineffective participation and involvement of local communities in the development of tourism (Dixey, 2008).

The unsustainability of community participation does not only occur in parts of the European world, but also in East Asia. Gili Trawangan is one of the tourism development areas in Lombok, Indonesia, which the government decided to develop as a marine nature park. Tourism development as a whole, however, may potentially have the tendency to marginalise the involvement of the local community. Gili Trawangan as an island destination is also vulnerable to natural disasters. This island is in the path of the Flores Ascending Fault (Flores Back Arc) which extends from East Nusa Tenggara (*Nusa Tenggara Timur*/NTT) to northern Bali. The earthquake in 2018 was one such natural disaster. This earthquake devastated Gili Trawangan on 5 August 2018, with a strength of 7 on the Richter scale (SR). But the next six months after the disaster has offered the island charm.

Many researchers also encourage the engagement and participation of society as a crucial and beneficial measure for sustainable tourism in the planning and growth

of tourism (Cárdenas, Byrd, & Duffy, 2015; Dogra & Gupta, 2012; McLoughlin & Hanrahan, 2019). The community has a role in protecting destinations by developing a sense of community participation. The sense of community needs to be reinforced by local communities for tourism growth (Conway & Hachen, 2005).

Despite its problems, the development of Gili Trawangan has been, and still is, a magnet for tourists to come to the island. Only a few have witnessed the synergy resulting from the empowerment of community participation and disaster recovery. Therefore, this paper seeks to explain and evaluate the forms in which community involvement and participation was implemented in tourism creation in and around Gili Trawangan after the disaster in 2018. This article is expected to be able to contribute ideas and recommendations in the development of knowledge related to community participation in the aftermath of a disaster.

Literature Review

Community Participation and Involvement in Tourism Development

Sustainable tourism is tourism which takes full account of its current and future economic, social, and environmental impacts and addresses the needs of tourists, the industry, the environment, and host communities (UNEP, 2005). Owing to a lack of understanding and information about tourism development, most groups in the local community shy away from participation. Lack of community participation has been an encumbrance in prevention, control, and intervention management. It typically restricts community members' participation in tourism growth planning and decision-making (Dogra & Gupta, 2012; Kala & Bagri, 2018; Okech, 2016). In addition, the lack of tourism expertise restricts community members from becoming the leaders of their community's tourism projects as well as succession planning for tourism growth, and many governments in developed countries have used this as an excuse to push community members from being involved in tourism development (Abdul Razzaq et al., 2011; Moscardo, 2008).

Community involvement is regarded as a means of grassroots democracy, where people are entitled to make decisions on topics that concern their lives directly (Burns, 2004). Host community participation and involvement as a corrective style to control tourism development has encouraged the goal of sustainable tourism creation through voluntary participation of the local communities (Bello, Carr, Lovelock, & Xu, 2017; Styliadis, Biran, Sit, & Szivas, 2014). Snyman (2012) promoted the concept of community-driven tourism, where community members manage tourism infrastructure and facilities in their region. Cole (2006) indicated that the local community finds favourable and unfavourable tourist outcomes, either directly or indirectly, or that its involvement is necessary to better deal with the impacts and to gain the advantages produced by tourism activities. Kala and Bagri (2018) supported greater advocacy for community involvement, better synchronisation among the government authorities concerned, local education and training, and the

need to determine unique strategies to promote local participation that is tailored to an evolving destination context.

There are three forms of community participation that can illustrate community involvement (Arnstein, 1969; Pretty, 1995; Tosun, 1999). According to Pretty (1995), the typology of community participation was divided into seven levels: (a) manipulative participation, (b) passive participation, (c) participation by consultation, (d) participation for material incentives, (e) factional participation, (f) interactive participation, and (g) self-mobilisation. Arnstein (1969) posited that the typology of community participation was divided into eight levels. Meanwhile, Tosun (1999) noted that the typology of community participation consisted of three levels: (1) spontaneous participation, (2) induced participation, and (3) coercive participation.

Tosun (2006) argued that forms of involvement contextualised the categorical term “community participation”, which enabled individuals, people, and host communities to participate at various levels (local, regional, or national) and in different ways. The most important thing probably lies in the power of the power distribution. In the context of general developmental studies, the typologies of community participation by Arnstein (1969) and Pretty (1995) were established. They were not linked to the economic field in particular. However, the typology by Tosun (1999) was planned especially for tourism. It defined each form of involvement of the group with a particular reference to tourism. Figure 1 shows a comparison of the community participation typologies by Arnstein, Pretty, and Tosun (1999).

7. Self-mobilisation	←	8. Citizen control	Degrees of Citizen Power	→	Spontaneous Participation Bottom-up; active participation; direct participation; participation in decision making, authentic participation; self-planning.	
6. Interactive participation		7. Delegated power				6. Partnership
5. Functional participation	←	5. Placation	Degrees of Citizen Tokenism	→	Induced Participation Top-down; passive; formal; mostly indirect; degree of tokenism, manipulation; pseudo-participation; participation in implementation and sharing benefits; choice between proposed alternatives and feedback.	
4. Participation for material incentives		4. Consultation				3. Informing
3. Participation by consultation		2. Therapy				Non-participation
2. Passive participation	1. Manipulation	→	Coercive Participation Top-down; passive; formal; mostly indirect; participation in implementation, but not necessarily sharing benefits; choice between proposed limited alternatives or no choice; paternalism; non-participation; high degree of tokenism and manipulation.			
1. Manipulative participation						
Pretty's (1995) typology of community participation		Arnstein's (1971) typology of community participation			Tosun's (1999a) typology of community participation	

Key: Corresponding categories in each typology ⇔ ⇐

Source: Tosun, 2006

Figure 1. Normative typologies of community participation

Tosun's Three-level Typology of Community Participation

- A. **Spontaneous participation** means community participation occurs voluntarily, without being pushed by outside parties. This is the optimal type of involvement by the society. For a detailed explanation, this type of participation is divided into several dimensions, including:
1. **Active participation**, whereby participation occurs if the community achieves its own goals and satisfaction.
 2. **Direct participation**, whereby there is direct interaction with the community to make decisions, and the community members can convey their aspirations directly.
 3. **Informal participation**, whereby interaction occurs outside the official status of participation between local leaders and community development parties.
 4. **Authentic participation**, whereby the community is aware that it has to be fully responsible for the decisions taken. It also expects a greater share of the development results. Normally, this participation type shows the involvement of local communities; they not only need a change in the field of national politics, but also want a change in the economic field.
- B. **Induced participation** essentially means there is support, there are orders, and it is officially approved. This participation type is most commonly encountered in developing countries, where the government has a major role in initiating participatory action through strategies to encourage and train local leaders into taking a leading role, building cooperation, and supporting communities. To provide a deeper understanding of this type of participation, it is divided into several sections as follows:
1. **Passive participation**, whereby the group participates only in the implementation, and does not engage in the decision-making process.
 2. **Indirect participation**, in which people do not convey their decisions directly, but through representatives of certain institutions or groups who are appointed in general.
 3. **Formal participation**, which is officially approved and has status. The rules and limits for participation are set by the government.
 4. **Pseudo participation**, whereby the community is not concerned with decision-making, but the community is included in the execution of decisions made by others.
- C. **Coercive participation** is the most extreme form of participation, whereby the community is obliged and manipulated by the authorities to get involved in

tourism development. In the short term, there may be immediate results. However, in the long term, this type of coercion will erode the support of the community. It will also not result in, or even invoke, the interest of the community to be involved in development activities.

The Geographic Scope of the Study

Gili Air, Gili Meno, and Gili Trawangan are part of a Marine Tourism Park (*Taman Wisata Perairan/TWP*), and are known collectively as the Gili Matra Marine Park (Gili Matra). This park has a total area of 2,954 hectares (ha), which includes:

- ± 175 ha of land area for Gili Air, with a circumference of ± 5 km
- ± 150 ha of land area for Gili Meno, with a circumference of ± 4 km, and
- ± 340 ha of land area for Gili Trawangan, with a circumference of ± 7.5 km.

The rest of the surrounding area is marine water. The locus of research is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Gili Matra Marine Park of Indonesia

Gili Matra has a latitude of 8° 20'–8° 23' South and a longitude of 116° 00'–116° 08' East. Gili Trawangan, which is the largest of the three islands, is located at the tip of Lombok Island. Gili Air and Gili Meno are the two smaller islands. This region can be categorised as semi-open inner islands. The Gili Matra region is protected by Lombok Island in the south-eastern part, and influenced by the Java Sea in the northern side, Lombok Strait in the western part, and Indonesian Throughflow coming from the Indian Ocean (Murdana, 2010; Sprintall, Potemra, Hautala, Bray, & Pandoe, 2003).

Gili Matra has a tropical climate that is influenced by rainy and dry seasons. The temperature in this area ranges from 200° C–320° C. Wet periods with a rainfall of 200 mm/month generally occur from December to February, while dry periods with a rainfall of below 10 mm/month occur in August and September. The highest monthly rainfall occurs in January and the lowest rainfall occurs in September.

Gili Trawangan is the most popular destination and is widely known as the party island. This island has long been the benchmark for Lombok tourism. So much so that, a holiday in Lombok is not complete without visiting Gili Trawangan. The island is beautiful and famed for its white sand and clean beaches. It is a very happening island, where tourists can enjoy lively night entertainment.

Among the three islands, Gili Trawangan has the widest area (2 km wide, and 3 km long), with a total area of about 340 ha. Tourists can tour the island by foot or bicycle. Alternatively, they can ride a traditional Lombok horse-drawn carriage called *cidomo* to enjoy the beauty of the island because there is no use of motorbikes or cars in the area (Halim, 2017).

Administratively, the Gili Matra region is part of the Pemenang Subdistrict in the North Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) province. Gili Trawangan is known as a natural area with the development of marine ecotourism. It is a Marine Tourism Park (TWP) area through the Decree of the Minister of Marine Affairs and Fisheries, Indonesia, No. Kep. 67/MEN/2009. In the planning and development of the Gili Trawangan area, many areas are identified as having vulnerabilities, by internal, external, and natural factors (Murdana, 2013, 2019). Gili Trawangan is also very vulnerable to excessive resource exploration (Pradjoko, Bachtiar, Matalatta, & Sugihartono, 2015; Santamarta, Naranjo, & Arraiza, 2014).

The population of tourist visits to Gili Trawangan and its surroundings has been increasing yearly. The following Figure 3 shows that from 2009 to 2017, the level of tourist visits was on the increase. In 2018, however, the arrival of tourists dropped significantly, but gradually increased again in 2019. The sharp decline of 2018 was caused by the impact of the earthquake that struck the island of Lombok in August of that year. Tourist visits in 2018 had declined to 30.72%, before rising by 8.76% in 2019. In 2020, tourist arrivals again fell greatly by 79.42%, this time due to the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic.

Source: Government Tourism Offices of the North Lombok Regency, 2020

Figure 3. Gili Matra tourist arrivals

As a Marine Tourism Park (TWP), Gili Trawangan has great potential, and it faces various opportunities and threats from internal and external factors in tourism development. Natural disasters are one of the biggest threats to the island's existence. In addition, the role of local communities in tourism development is very important. The success of the development is tantamount to the participation of the local communities. The forms of participation and involvement of the local communities is the goal of this study, with regard to the recovery and sustainability of Gili Trawangan as a tourist destination.

Materials and Methods

This study used a purposive sampling approach in determining the respondent allocation. Purposive sampling was one of the non-random sampling techniques applied, where the researchers determined sampling by ascertaining specific characteristics in line with the research objectives. The aim was for the study to be able to answer research problems as expected (Sugiyono, 2011). Purposive sampling was used in an in-depth exploration of information to respondents, who were really familiar with the implementation of community participation and involvement in Gili Trawangan and its surroundings. Observation, thorough interviews, and an empirical study were the data collection approaches used. Participatory observation was employed and it included an observation checklist in the data collection process. The empirical study and in-depth interviews were combined to obtain more complete and accurate data. The samples included several key respondents, namely the lead of the Gili Trawangan Community Forum (*Forum Masyarakat Gili Trawangan/FMGT*), the lead of the Gili Trawangan Entrepreneurs Association (*Asosiasi Pengusaha Gili Trawangan/APGT*), the Head of Gili Eco Trust, the Head

of Gili Trawangan Hamlet, and the Chairman of the Gili Hotel Association (GHA). The qualitative approach was used in the study during the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data. This approach was chosen because qualitative research is a research method aimed at understanding human issues in a social context, generating a complete, nuanced image, reporting a comprehensive view of information sources, and performing them naturally, without researchers interfering (Sudaryono, 2019).

Results and Discussions

The first part of this section focuses on Gili Trawangan and its surroundings that suffered significant damage after the earthquake in August 2018. The island, which was previously a vibrant place where people had fun, was reduced to devastation and ruin and left totally devoid of tourists. The residents busied themselves packing and salvaging what was left of their belongings in the wake of the disaster. Supporting facilities and tourism infrastructure were all damaged. Almost everyone who had survived the incident was shocked and shaken; others experienced severe trauma. Some people were dedicated to Gili Trawangan, choosing to stay on to protect the island and take care of its remaining resources. Communities voluntarily carried out clean-ups, repairs, and various island restoration activities in mutual cooperation. The community recovery movement was spontaneous. Cleaning was done on access roads that were filled with building debris due to the tremor. In some places, the community set up emergency tents for temporary shelter. At night, the island—dark and deserted—seemed tense.

Based on the observation and empirical study conducted from September 2018 till December 2018, the researchers confirmed that *adat* (traditional institution) as a village community institution and the non-governmental organisations (NGOs) in Gili Trawangan played a significant role. They executed active recovery collaboratively. They also encouraged and developed the spirit of community to recovery. This spirit of community has been proven capable of generating a sense of solidarity to awaken and perform destination recovery.

This research thus found that the earthquake had contributed positively to growing and strengthening the spirit of the community to protect and help each other in developing Gili Trawangan and its surroundings. These research results reinforced the findings made by Conway and Hachen (2005) that developing and strengthening a sense of community was capable of protecting and sustaining tourism destinations.

The research also found that the involvement and participation of the Gili Trawangan community arose spontaneously, due to the members' awareness and responsibility to protect and maintain the Gili Trawangan destination. The findings were analysed based on the typology of community participation (Tosun, 1999). These

findings both endorsed and reinforced Tosun's concept of community involvement in tourism. In fact, in accordance with Tosun's typology of community participation, the findings revealed that spontaneous participation was developed from the bottom up, direct participation, participation in decision-making, authentic participation, and self-planning (Tosun, 2006). Meanwhile, induced and coercive participations did not occur in Gili Trawangan's community during the research. Induced participation is characterised by top-down participation, formality, mostly indirect, a degree of tokenism, manipulation, pseudo-participation, participation in implementation and sharing of benefit, and the choice between proposed alternatives and feedback. On the other hand, coercive participation is characterised by top-down participation, formality, mostly indirect, participation in implementation (but not necessarily in sharing of benefit), the choice between proposed limited alternatives and no choice, paternalism, non-participation, a high degree of tokenism, and manipulation (Tosun, 2005, 2006).

The implementation of community involvement and participation was carried out through (1) an image and education approach, (2) a mythological and cultural approach, and (3) an annual event approach. Implementation of community participation using the image and education approach essentially means that the community was directly involved in the planning and development of Gili Trawangan. Image implementation took place in the form of the Safe Gili campaign, Gili triathlon, weekly clean-ups, and coral reef plastic clean-ups.

The Safe Gili campaign aimed to show the world that the Gili islands were safe to visit. It was proven that the community and tourists were not fearful of the disaster, and had collaborated in conducting sports exhibitions, clean-ups, and marine conservation in Gili Trawangan and its surroundings. The community and NGOs were in collaboration; not only in participatory action, but also in the sharing of event expenses.

The mythological and cultural approach aimed to involve the community in the development of tourism cultural aspects. The implementation of the mythological and cultural approach was done through traditional activities, such as *gili megibung* and *mandi safar*. *Gili megibung* is the traditional approach to community involvement and participation of maintaining solidarity through eating together. Apart from that, all materials and equipment must use a natural traditional approach. Materials made of plastic were prohibited. The essence of the event was community learning, collaboration, and participation to care for and protect nature.

Meanwhile, *mandi safar* or *rebo bontong* is one of the traditional rituals of the Gili people which originated from Bugis. The aim of the ritual was to purify themselves by bathing in the sea together through a traditional process. In general, the purpose of the mythological and cultural approach was to balance and sustain nature.

The study results also found a significant relationship between the spirit of the community through a sense of solidarity and community involvement and participation as a salient point of sustainable tourism, especially after an earthquake or a natural disaster. Community spirit and the spontaneous actions of community participation in Gili Trawangan and its surroundings were strongly influenced by several factors, including (1) the similarity of emotional relationships due to the disaster, (2) the feeling of a Bugis tribe family, (3) the influence of *adat* power through several NGOs in Gili Trawangan and its surroundings, (4) the integrity and hope of island recovery and economy, and (5) a responsibility-based culture.

The factors that influence direct and spontaneous community participation in Gili Trawangan and its surroundings are proposed as a recommendation to policymakers in formulating future actions for sustainable tourism. Theoretically, research findings can upgrade scientific knowledge, especially in the implementation of community involvement and participation linked to sustainable tourism, and can reinforce the theory used.

Conclusion

Although community participation has been considered one of the effective strategies as well as a salient point of sustainable tourism, the fact remains: its success hinges extensively on the factors influencing the spirit of community participation. There is an interplay between collective spirit and community engagement after the tragedy. The implementation of community involvement and participation in Gili Trawangan and its surroundings has been encouraged by direct and spontaneous participation. Community power has dominant influence on the planning and development of Gili Trawangan as a tourism destination. *Adat* and the NGOs of Gili Trawangan acted as the initiator and executor of responsible development. Nevertheless, this research has its limitations, with regard to the method of data collection and sampling method to support the value achievement of justification. Future research is recommended to reconstruct the study using the quantitative approach so that it is more measurable.

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1. Associate Prof. Dr. Sandeep K. Walia (Lovely Professional University, India).
Email: *sndp.walia551@gmail.com*
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9. Dr. Jeetesh Kumar (Universiti Utara Malaysia, Malaysia).
Email: *jeetesh.kumar@taylor.edu.my*
10. Associate Prof. Dr. Noor Azimin Zainol (Universiti Utara Malaysia, Malaysia).
Email: *azimin@uum.edu.my*
11. Associate Prof. Dr. Basri Abdul Rashid (Universiti Utara Malaysia, Malaysia).
Email: *basri@uum.edu.my*
12. Associate Prof. Dr. Azila Azmi (Universiti Teknologi MARA, Malaysia).
Email: *azila.azmi@uitm.edu.my*
13. Dr Mohd Hashim (Universiti Teknologi MARA, Malaysia).
Email: *hashim@uitm.edu.my*
14. Dr. Hafiz Hanafiah (Universiti Teknologi MARA, Malaysia).
Email: *hafizhanafiah@uitm.edu.my*
15. Associate Prof. Dr. Hassanal Bahar Pengiran Bagul (Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Malaysia). Email: *hbagul@ums.edu.my*
16. Dr. Norhanim Abdul Razak (Universiti Utara Malaysia, Malaysia).
Email: *norhanim@uum.edu.my*
17. Dr Norashikin Mohd Nor (Universiti Utara Malaysia, Malaysia).
Email: *norashikin@uum.edu.my*
18. Dr. Gelareh Aboali (Universiti Utara Malaysia, Malaysia).
Email: *gelareh@uum.edu.my*
19. Dr Edwin Mohammed (Universiti Utara Malaysia, Malaysia).
Email: *edwin@uum.edu.my*
20. Associate Prof. Dr Kamal Izzuwan Ramli (Universiti Utara Malaysia, Malaysia).
Email: *izzuwan@uum.edu.my*

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ASEAN TOURISM RESEARCH ASSOCIATION (ATRA)

ATRA or Asean Tourism Research Organization aims to support the ASEAN integration policies through tourism research and innovation, enhance collaboration on tourism for the academia and researchers within and outside ASEAN by establishing a network of tourism research clusters in Institutions of Higher learning from the region.

Mission and Vision

- Establishing a network of Tourism research clusters in ASEAN Universities.
- Developing links between ASAEAN researchers in tourism with common projects.
- Providing a recognized multi-site resource and expertise related to ASEAN Tourism.
- Contributing to the development of the Tourism Human capacity for ASEAN Countries.
- Supporting the ASEAN integration policies.

Objectives

Scope of Activities

In pursuance of the aims and objectives defined above the Association shall:

- Carry out research related to tourism in ASEAN.
- Organize seminars, forums, symposiums, exhibitions, workshops and conferences, carry out studies, research and raise issues in accordance with the objectives of the Association.
- Integrate, publish and disseminate materials, such as books, research reports and periodicals relevant to the tourism industry in ASEAN and other activities pertaining to the promotion of the objectives stated above.
- Maintain a database of tourism research expertise with a focus on ASEAN.
- Assist members of the association to find the right expertise and clusters for research collaborations in compliance with the objectives of the association.
- Accept and raise grants, endowments and financial support from available legitimate sources in support of its programmes and activities.
- Collaborate with other recognized associations or bodies within or outside ASEAN, which subscribe to the associations objectives.

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